

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR THE EFFECTIVE ACHIEVEMENT OF THE LEARNING PROCESS

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Annotation In this article explain self-study of the student, carried out under the guidance of an experienced English teacher, is entered into the schedule with hours. The volume of these hours should not be less than the total volume of contact hours of practical classes and seminars allotted for the discipline "Foreign Language". And all other hours of independent work of the student must be confirmed by the proposed tasks of the teacher. All this, undoubtedly, optimizes the cognitive activity and independence of students.

Key words: self-study, function, activity, effectiveness, process, content, planning, approaches.

Аннотация В данной статье поясняется самостоятельная работа студента, проводимая под руководством опытного преподавателя английского языка, внесенная в расписание с указанием часов. Объем этих часов не должен быть меньше общего объема контактных часов практических занятий и семинаров, отведенных по дисциплине «Иностранный язык». А все остальные часы самостоятельной работы обучающегося должны быть подтверждены предложенными заданиями преподавателя. Все это, несомненно, оптимизирует познавательную деятельность и самостоятельность учащихся.

Ключевые слова: самообучение, функция, деятельность, эффективность, процесс, содержание, планирование, подходы.

The development and management of self-education should not only be aimed at regulating the necessary properties of the subject of self-educational activity, but also self-regulate by it, so it can be argued that this phenomenon has a sign of ergodicity. The development and management of self-education assumes partnership interaction as its leading function, while the dialogic nature of this process is due to:

- firstly, its humanistic orientation;
- and secondly, the modern requirements of the time, and especially the necessary transition to an individually oriented organization of the educational process.

The functions of a teacher in joint educational activities with students - from planning, organizing, guiding and controlling at the initial stage of the formation of self-educational competence of students, are transformed at higher levels of pedagogical management of self-education into a coordinating, recommendatory, orienting one [1]. At the same time, the participation of the teacher is reduced in terms of direct contact with students and, at the same time, it increases and becomes more complicated in terms of providing the student with the necessary information support for him to implement the content of independent work. The activity of the student, in turn, begins to acquire more and more activity, namely, from the perceiving, copying role, in the future, there is a transition to active independent actions in terms of organizing, planning, controlling and adjusting their own activities.

It is important to emphasize that the content of self-education acts as a socially and personally determined, fixed in pedagogical science and state educational standards, an idea of social experience to be mastered [2]. For this reason, the modeling of the content of self-education in English at non-linguistic faculties is based on the resources of the pedagogical management of self-educational activities.

In the history of the development and management of educational systems in the process of learning English at non-linguistic faculties, two approaches to the

problem of goal setting can be distinguished: formative (projective) and free. The formative approach is based on the fact that the highest goal of education is the most complete satisfaction of the requirements of the state for the individual, for the graduate, who must master a foreign language. In this approach, the interests of the state come first. The second approach - free goal-setting - involves the creation of conditions for the maximum development of the abilities of each individual, its ascent to the highest human aspirations, life ideals and priorities, in other words, the maximum development of those human properties that are determined by the needs of the individual [3].

The specificity of the pedagogical support of the student's self-educational activity in the process of learning English at non-linguistic faculties consists in the optimal creation of pedagogical conditions for the student's free goal-setting and the choice of adequate goals for self-educational activity, as well as the content, methods, means and forms of its achievement. The efficiency of the self-education process increases with the obligatory fulfillment of a schematically built set of pedagogical conditions, which contains a set of necessary interrelated measures of the pedagogical process, subject to which the achievement of predetermined goals and objectives of education is ensured.

A set of pedagogical conditions for the effective achievement of the learning process

Competence of an English teacher

Having timely feedback

Availability of sources in the library resources of the university for independent work by students

The combination of individual, collective and group forms of organization of the pedagogical process

The use of a variety of teaching methods in combination with the way of activity, taking into account the individual characteristics and the initial level of preparedness of each student

Career guidance of disciplines and the depth of profiling of certain disciplines (taking into account the multi-level division of future professionals into bachelors and masters)

Stimulation of regular cognitive activity of students, which is a simulation of students' own learning activities

Monitoring of knowledge control, including diagnostics and assessment of the quality of the results of the activities of the subjects of pedagogical interaction, based on the results of which the teacher can clarify the goals and content of training, review approaches to choosing the organization of forms and methods of teaching and individual stages of the technological chain

The development and management of the student's own educational activities can significantly intensify the work on self-education and self-development, bring students closer to creativity. To develop and manage their own educational activities, students need to:

- to realize the purpose of the upcoming cognitive activity, to comprehend and internally accept its motives;
- highlight the amount of self-educational material to be studied;
- plan the sequence of its study;
- to determine the ways of self-education for mastering this self-educational material;
- choose the means and didactic technologies for the implementation of cognitive activity.

The conditions for the success of a student in the process of developing and managing their own educational activities in the process of learning English, we include:

- a conscious desire for self-education in accordance with the individual characteristics and needs of society;
- sufficient level of self-educational competence;
- the availability of language support and operational assistance in developing the trajectory of self-education;
- an adequate self-assessment of one's own achievements, based on introspection and reflection, which allows one to see the achieved individual result;
- self-control and self-correction of cognitive activity.

The self study of the student, carried out under the guidance of an experienced English teacher, is entered into the schedule with hours. The volume of these hours should not be less than the total volume of contact hours of practical classes and seminars allotted for the discipline "Foreign Language". And all other hours of independent work of the student must be confirmed by the proposed tasks of the teacher. All this, undoubtedly, optimizes the cognitive activity and independence of students. With all this, the main efforts of English language teachers will be aimed at meeting the requirements of the mandatory standard and the appropriate organization of self-educational work.

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